

Participatory evaluations: easier said than done?

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SUMMARY

They have been part of the evaluation repertoire for 50 years, yet they are still presented as innovative: participatory evaluations may be old, but they are still rare in reality. Here we look back at the main obstacles encountered in practice: an ambiguous definition, the fear it generates among decision-makers and the difficulty of maintaining the participatory dimension throughout the evaluation. However, it is well worth the effort, and participatory evaluation has a future as a starting point for future redesigns of public action.

KEYWORDS

Participatory evaluation; evaluation practice; conflictuality

INTRODUCTION

There is a real paradox with participatory evaluation (PE). On the one hand, the issue of stakeholder participation in evaluation is almost as old as evaluation itself (BRISOLARA 1998; RIDDE 2006, 23). On the other hand, it continues to be presented as a new solution to the recurring problems of public policy evaluation.

As early as the 1970s, it was possible to identify evaluations in which stakeholders played an important role (COUSINS AND WHITMORE 1998). The 1980s and 1990s saw the development of a large body of arguments in favour of participation in evaluation, and on ways of organising this participation. Participatory approaches took off in Europe in the 1990s, initially at the level of projects and programmes, before finding their way into national evaluation policies (from 1991 in France) and into the principles and standards of many evaluation societies around the world.

So why is PE regularly presented as an innovation, despite 50 years of experience¹? The fact is that, while participation may well be present in rhetoric, it is rarely present in practice. Based on our experience as PE practitioners in France and Europe, we can identify three reasons for this:

- The ambiguity surrounding the term PE means that it is often difficult, at first glance, to know what you are dealing with.
- The second reason is that PE is dangerous for the actors in charge; it challenges the frameworks and the way in which public policy is conducted.
- And thirdly, even with the best of intentions, PEs are difficult to implement, because the context, the choice of participants and chance all play an important role in their success. In the end, PE is not a guaranteed product and can lead to disappointment (BARON AND MONNIER 2003).

Does this mean we should be discouraged? On the contrary, participation is one of the keys to ensuring that evaluation remains relevant in the decade ahead, insofar as it succeeds in tackling certain fundamental issues, which we will discuss in conclusion.

1. WHAT IS PARTICIPATORY EVALUATION?

1.1 A restrictive definition

Conducting a PE is not simply a matter of involving stakeholders in the assessment. J. Bradley Cousins and E. Whitmore have proposed three criteria to distinguish PE from other approaches involving stakeholders (COUSINS AND WHITMORE 1998; for details of these criteria and their operationalisation: MARCHAND 2018; RIDDE 2006) : *control of the*

1 For example, PE is presented as an innovation already present in France in 1987 (Baron and Monnier 2003) ; an innovative practice in 2009 (JACOB AND OUVRARD 2009); and very recently in 2020 as an “emerging trend” (LEMIRE, PECK, AND POROWSKI 2020) .

evaluation process, selection of stakeholders and extent of participation. When applied to our professional evaluation practice, this would lead to the following definition:

- **the PE gives a pluralistic entity (usually a committee) a decision-making role in the technical conduct of the evaluation** (design, steering, decisions on implementation, data collection, reporting, etc.). This control may be total or shared with the sponsors and the evaluation team; it may relate to all or some of the stages described above.
- By *pluralistic*, we mean that **this committee must include points of view other than those of the decision-makers, funders or operators**, and in particular those of those involved in implementation, of the public affected by the public action, or concerned as citizens.
- **this committee must be involved in the production of the evaluation**, at the very least in the way in which the intervention will be judged, in terms of what values and criteria ('what counts, what is important?'), and in the response given by the evaluation to the questions asked to it.

The participatory dimension cannot simply be deduced from the initial characteristics of an evaluation: it is assessed retrospectively. Thus, control can be *given to* the pluralistic committee, be *taken* during the exercise... or it can disappear if it is not used. Pluralism depends on maintaining participation in the evaluation process, and on the ability of stakeholders to express different points of view; it can be lost if one stakeholder gains the upper hand (CHANUT 2002, 12). Finally, it is not enough for participants to express their views or testify on the constituent elements of the evaluation. **The committee must be a place for evaluative deliberation, i.e. a place for a reasoned exchange of arguments in which all the participants have a say.** This process allows them not only to be informed, but also to develop their preferences, in terms of what is important to them, and therefore to arrive at a more informed judgement.

As this is an evaluation, the deliberation must:

- be guided by a concern to arrive at a judgement based on evidence gathered during the evaluation;
- focus on the (un)expected consequences of the intervention in the real world, and not just on the intervention process or its theoretical benefits or drawbacks;
- aim to improve public action and, *ultimately*, contribute to the general interest.

Excluded from this process are mechanisms which, while perfectly respectable, are more collaborative than participatory², as well as participatory mechanisms that can use evaluation as an excellent pretext for organising exchanges (citizens' conferences, citizens'

² For the distinction between "collaborative" and "participatory" see MARCHAND (2018).

juries, etc.), but which are not evaluative, even if they bear the name³. Figure 1 below summarises these definitions:

Figure 1: Definition based on three characteristics of the evaluation committee

Beyond these three conditions, there is still a very wide diversity of PEs, which can have very different characteristics. In particular, we will distinguish between evaluations that bring together a wide range of stakeholders, with the aim of getting them to exchange views, and evaluations that bring together a particular type of stakeholder (frontline workers, the public concerned) so that they can deliberate amongst themselves and make their voices heard.

1.2 The promise of participatory evaluation

Why bother? **As participatory mechanisms, PEs generally serve three main stated objectives, which are to improve public action; to ‘live together’, to interest people and stakeholders in the collective interest; and to supplement our democratic systems, or even eventually replace them, by changing the balance of power in our societies.** We might add that there are also unspoken objectives, which may come under the heading of communication, ‘pedagogy’⁴, or clientelism.

When applying these frameworks to PE, two approaches are possible (COUSINS AND WHITMORE 1998):

- Seeing participation first and foremost as a means of producing better, more relevant and more credible assessments (HOULE 2018; and see J. Leca, quoted in

3 In our experience, the criticisms raised about PE, i.e. regarding its low technicality or subjective nature, often relate to this type of evaluations. For a presentation of these criticisms, see JACOB AND OUVRARD 2009.

4 For a European example, see EURÉVAL (2009).

LASCOUMES, VARONE, AND PONS 2006, 22) , more legitimate (MONNIER AND DURAN 1992, 24) and therefore more useful and more widely used: this is the ‘practical vision’ of PE (COUSINS 2003; MARCHAND 2018; PLOTTU AND PLOTTU 2009; RIDDE 2006) .

- Or an approach that focuses on giving stakeholders, especially those who do not usually have a voice, the means to make themselves heard. Evaluation helps them to strengthen their knowledge, to understand each other better, to work together, and even to gain self-esteem and critical awareness—in short, the power to act⁵. This is the ‘transformative’ logic of PE.

1.3 Three examples of PE

That's the theory, but what is the reality? Below are three very different examples in which we have been involved, which illustrate the diversity of EP.

(1) The evaluation of a regional scheme designed to support social cohesion projects by residents of deprived neighbourhoods began by adopting a fairly traditional collaborative approach to identifying the benefits of these projects to residents through a series of case studies in the areas concerned. The evaluation team concluded that the programme was valued but little known, little used and with largely intangible impacts. It questioned whether the scheme should continue. A citizen panel, representative of the regional population, was then recruited to answer a series of evaluation questions. Accompanied by the same team, the citizens were trained and their reflections were fed by the data and analyses collected during the initial evaluation. They interviewed stakeholders (experts, agents, social workers, etc.) whom they had selected beforehand in order to prepare their citizens' opinion. In their opinion, they did not hesitate to distance themselves from the evaluation questions and to assert that social cohesion was not just an issue for disadvantaged neighbourhoods, but for all areas of the region. In this way, they put the relevance of the programme before its effectiveness. During the feedback process, the elected representative committed to the public and the local media to take their views into account. A year later, the citizens were invited to see what progress has been made.

(2) To evaluate urban transport in a large city, a pluralistic body was convened. It included elected representatives, staff from the commissioning authority and other authorities involved, and associations representing different categories of users. The evaluation questions, which were rather vague, were set out in the terms of reference (ToR). At the first meeting of the panel, the ToR were discussed and amended, but only marginally. For the Department of Transport, this evaluation was not really necessary:

5 According to William Ninacs, reported by RIDDE (2006).

“everything is fine”. However, exploratory interviews with local stakeholders revealed a number of issues that needed to be addressed. These were downplayed by the commissioner, but external stakeholders pointed out that these issues were important to them, triggering in-depth analysis. The presentation of the findings, followed by the conclusions, gave rise to very lively but constructive debates about interpretation: in the end, the commissioner decided to endorse the evaluation judgement (rather than leaving it to the evaluation committee or the service provider), considering that it was legitimate enough and a good basis for future discussion with stakeholders. The stakeholders expressed their wish to continue discussions with the commissioning authority on the basis of the evaluation. The City leader, attacked by his political opponents over the results of the evaluation, replied that no one had forced him to carry out an evaluation and that the nuanced results presented were evidence of his administration's ability to question itself.

(3) The French government was experimenting with collective action by the Labour Inspectorate (LI) with the aim of bringing about a massive improvement in the situation of workers in a given area, for example exposure to asbestos on building sites. This represented a significant change in the LI's professional practice, which was based on a territorial rather than a thematic approach. It was inconceivable in the culture of this administration that an outsider could come in and judge the merits or consequences of their actions. Thus, although the initial mandate was rather narrow (essentially the definition of indicators), the contracting authority and the evaluation team agreed on an approach in which the members of the LI themselves would design and implement their evaluation system, through an action training organised in parallel with the initial phases of the experiment. For each collective action⁶, they developed a programme theory for the collective actions, formulated their evaluation questions and designed adapted collection tools. At the end of the experiment, some of them would commission additional data collection commissioned by an external service provider. The report was written by a member of the LI team, with the help of the external team, and discussed collectively with colleagues. These evaluations were formative for the LI teams and gave them additional weight to assert themselves in the face of their ministry's directives. Locally, they were useful for improving future actions. But this type of approach was difficult to disseminate outside the areas that initially volunteered, especially without the support of an external evaluation team.

The table below compares the three cases in terms of the definition of PE and its consequences.

6 These actions, carried out at local level, focused on reducing exposure of workers to asbestos on building sites, ensuring that ambulance drivers comply with working hours, and guaranteeing health and safety rules in the retail sector.

Table 1: Comparative analysis of the three cases

Case	(1) cohesion	(2) transport	(3) labour
<i>Multiple stakeholders</i>	Citizen panel	Decision-makers, operators, other local authorities, user representatives (NGOs)	LI members involved in the actions
<i>Control</i>	In theory, framed by a mandate of the authority, but citizens have gone beyond it	In theory given to the committed, then affirmed by the committee during the evaluation process	No control in theory, but taken by LI to make the evaluative process possible
<i>Evaluation deliberation</i>	Through a citizens' jury process	Within the committee, with a specific moderation process	By carrying out the evaluation themselves
<i>Ambition</i>	Practical	Practical	Transformative
<i>Contribution of the participatory dimension to evaluation</i>	Modification of the evaluation questions, scope broadened to encompass the whole regional territory, prioritisation of the relevance criterion Requirement for the sponsor to account for decisions following the evaluation	Joint identification of collective issues to investigate, shared ownership of the diagnosis and agreement on the judgement Strong credibility of the evaluation, a legitimate basis for continuing discussions and producing a shared policy	Explanation of the assumptions underlying the collective actions' theories Access to the field and stakeholders' interpretations (impossible with an external evaluator) Credibility of the evaluation for other LI members
<i>Benefits for participants</i>	Better perception of public action, willingness to pursue citizen involvement	Better understanding of other stakeholders' points of view. For NGOs, the decision to act on their own, without waiting for the authorities to act For elected representatives, an element of credibility with the general public	Acquiring practical skills. Development of an evaluative stance on the part of LI members that was very different from their usual "juridic" stance. A tool for the construction of a collective.

2. PARTICIPATIVE EVALUATION: BEWARE THE DANGER

If these promises and examples were anything to go by, PE should be widespread, but this is not the case: there are still very few of them. A few years ago, the *Société française d'évaluation* looked at a sample of 224 evaluations to analyse how stakeholders were involved. Of these 224 evaluations, 131, or 58%, involved the beneficiaries of public action in one way or another. They were in a position to co-decide on the content of the evaluation in 7 of them, i.e. 3% of the initial sample.⁷

This is not to paint an overly negative a picture. Most evaluators recognise the importance of involving stakeholders (MATHISON 2005, quoted by RIDDE 2006), and this seems to be the case for commissioners too. We have moved beyond the stage where evaluation could be seen as a one-to-one meeting between a decision-maker and a neutral, objective evaluator imbued with the general interest. In our experience, evaluation commissioners are increasingly willing to go beyond gathering information from stakeholders. Inviting external figures to the steering committee is often viewed as a guarantee of credibility, as are workshops involving the targets of public action or intended beneficiaries. All this is by no means an innovation, and must be recognised as the norm, to which exceptions are made when circumstances require.

Except that this is what sponsors now label as PE. The vagueness surrounding the term means that we can avoid thinking too much about its implications⁸.

In our experience, only a few highly committed local authorities, administrations or associations, which often already have a previous culture of evaluation or participation, knowingly request PEs. Elsewhere, decision-makers are often afraid of losing control of the process, and rightly so, as in the case of citizen evaluation (1), which forces a decision-maker to take a stance on an unanticipated issue, or that of urban transport (2), which provides stakeholders with a solid basis for demanding changes in the policy pursued by the local authority. However, in both cases, this loss of control has contributed to the credibility of the evaluation in both cases, as well as to its usefulness.

If we really want to reap the benefits of PE, we need to get out of this ambiguity. In the short term, as evaluators, we have a responsibility to use the 'zone of autonomy' that an evaluation provides to push the cursor towards more participation where possible and relevant (DELAHAIS AND DEVAUX-SPATARAKIS 2018). However, for this choice to be legitimate, it must be shared and justified: the sponsors must be able to understand what participation really means, its concrete consequences (sharing of control, openness, organisation of deliberation, etc.), but also what it enables for evaluation and public action. This is what happened in evaluation (3), where we convinced the sponsor to give LIs full power over the content of the evaluation, convinced that this was the only way to prevent

7 This figure does not necessarily represent all PE in France, as the calculation is based on a sample in certain sectors, and certain fields, notably social action, which are more welcoming to PE than others (SFE 2016) .

8 This phenomenon is well known in the world of participation (BLONDIAUX AND SINTOMER 2002) .

them from boycotting the process, and to ensure that the evaluations were completed and useful.

In the longer term, the (in)ability of decision-makers to take risks should no longer be a criterion for launching a PE (CLOT 2015). Worst-case scenarios are possible, but they are rare⁹. We now need to get into the habit of institutional procedures, but we also need to find a 'routine' so that the dimensions of participation are no longer analysed as risks, but as ingredients whose dosage varies according to context and needs.

3. THE DEVIL IS IN THE DETAIL

Last but not least, it's not easy to get a PE through to the end. There are two main pitfalls: losing sight of participation, and losing sight of evaluation. A PE must be able to derive its legitimacy from these two aspects¹⁰, but this makes it more complex to conduct. The following section looks at a number of key issues relating to the implementation of these evaluations.

3.1 Participatory expression doesn't happen by itself

Launching a PE is making the bet that a group of stakeholders, who are not evaluation professionals, can play an essential role in structuring and producing the evaluation. However, this is far from obvious. The members of the committee may be reluctant to take control of the evaluation process, even if it is given to them. And evaluative deliberation is a demanding activity. **In other words, it is easy to respect the forms of the PE by asking the committee for its opinion, but not giving it the means to express it.**

Evaluators who really want to reap the benefits of participation therefore have to work on three fronts in the limited time available for the evaluation. They must¹¹:

- increase the skills of stakeholders, both in terms of evaluation and the evaluation's subject-matter,
- provide opportunities for stakeholders to exercise collective control over the evaluation, and to deliberate...
- ... while at the same time generating interest and commitment to the approach throughout, so that participants remain involved throughout the process.

9 See the example of the regional nature parks that followed the recommendations of a PE that involved the park's inhabitants, but had to backtrack under pressure from influential players (*Monnier, Varone and Sage 2008, 251*).

10 Jean-Claude Barbier points out that the PEs set up in France by the *Conseil Scientifique de l'Évaluation* in the 1990s had both scientific and political legitimacy (Barbier 2010) .

11 For analysis purposes, we use the COM-B framework proposed by Susan Michie, Maartje M. van Stralen and Robert West (2011). There are many resources available on the conditions for successful PEs, see Isabelle Bourgeois and Marthe Hurteau (2018) and Steve Jacob and Laurence Ouvrard (2009).

These elements take various forms. For example, the citizens involved in the evaluation (1) and the LI members involved in the evaluation (3) received training before the start of the evaluation, whereas for the members of the evaluation committee (2), we preferred to include explanations on evaluation concepts throughout the evaluation process. In this last evaluation, the stakeholders were initially unable to participate in the discussion on the evaluation questions: we had to give them a new opportunity to do so by providing them with a series of potential, very concrete issues, such as the use of public transport by young pensioners, or night-time services, so that the committee could assert itself collectively.

3.2 The different roles of the evaluator

In PE, the evaluation team must combine requirements in terms of robustness of analysis and quality of participation, which Éric Monnier summarised under the triple figure of *methodologist*, *mediator* and *midwife* (1992). This means, firstly, that they must have skills in leading and conducting discussions, including interpersonal skills (PATTON 2018), but also that they must be careful about their positioning, which sometimes borders on that of a tightrope walker. For example, in evaluation (1), the citizens were trained on the basis of the findings of our initial evaluation, but they also had to come to their own conclusions (which would in fact be quite different from ours): we had to remain neutral even though we had already made a judgement.

Another difficulty is that participatory deliberation is largely based on the work carried out by the evaluation team. In evaluation (2), a “colored vote” workshop¹² was organised at the end of the evaluation to discuss the conclusions we had drawn. These were deliberately sharp to make it easier for participants to express themselves, but in return, some of them complained that we were not sufficiently nuanced in our judgements. We then had to reveal our stratagem so that the debate would not be about the team's work, but about the conclusions of the evaluation.

An essential aspect of this work is its very practical dimension. A wide range of participatory tools is now available¹³, and these are invaluable: for instance, the citizens' conference set up as part of the evaluation (1) provided a complete framework for the evaluation. However, the existing guides can explain the objectives and methods of participation, but they cannot account for the excessive weight of detail to be considered: the arrangement of the rooms, the clarity of the rules, the form of the tools, the way in which they are presented, the attitude of the moderator... tiny elements, but which often make the difference between a successful moment of participation and a failed one.¹⁴

12 The aim of this tool is to highlight the differences of opinion between voters, so that discussions can focus on the points of disagreement.

13 For an example, see BILODEAU (2006).

14 On the importance of these aspects in a participative approach, see QUADRANT CONSEIL(2020).

3.3 What participation at what stages?

Because this deliberative work is complicated and time-consuming, and because it is not possible to mobilise the body on a permanent basis, the choice is often made to focus the interactions on key aspects, such as questioning or judgement. This sets aside a number of technical aspects, particularly methodological, which are left to the discretion of the assessor and the client.

Even in the most participatory evaluations, participants generally rely on the evaluation team to manage methodological issues (PATTON 2018, 126). So we tend to impose the technical choices of data collection and analysis, and these choices are obviously not neutral. Figure2 below shows the level of stakeholder involvement at the various stages of the evaluation. In evaluations (1) and (2), they do not have control over the methodology. Their ability to guide the data collection is also limited. It is only in (3) that the members of the IT have more latitude, conducting their own evaluation within a framework established for them. We note that the logic of public procurement, within which a large number of evaluations are carried out today, is a limiting factor from this point of view. Indeed, the methodological approach is a factor in the choice between several commercial proposals; the service provider, for his part, bases its financial estimate on a precise budget and timetable. In addition to the existing tools, we probably need to invent more flexible partnership arrangements so that the stakeholders can be more involved in the technical choices made during the evaluation.

Figure2: Stakeholder involvement in the different phases of the evaluation (solid line: strong involvement; dotted line: partial; white: no involvement)

4. SOME NEW FRONTIERS FOR PE

This final section looks at why PE is 'worth the effort'.

4.1 How could we not do a PE?

Perhaps the first step is to turn the question on its head. There are situations today where it is no longer possible to carry out a proper evaluation, let alone a useful one, if it is not participatory. Here are *at least* two such situations:

First of all, there are all these policies that are now being imposed on those for whom they are intended. **We may call them “beneficiaries”, but the benefit is more often in the eyes of the public authorities than in that of the people concerned,** especially when it comes to marginalised groups: Roma, refugees, prisoners, people living in deprived neighbourhoods, people with disabilities, the unemployed, dependent elderly... But these are also the people who don't vote, who know they are ill-equipped for debate and have given up –or never considered– the idea of putting forward their ideas in a public arena. Not only should we adhere to the ethical principle “Nothing should be done for them without them” (ROBERT ET AL. 2018), but even without adhering to the moral aspect of this principle, we must recognise that without this participation we run the risk of losing the essential capacity as evaluators to take a step to the side, to re-interrogate in depth the values and underlying assumptions of policies, but also our own – especially when we have the same education, when we come from the same background as those who hold the levers of public decision-making.

But participation is not just for marginalised groups. We live in societies where actors are increasingly reflexive. In most social programmes, the agents who implement the actions and interact with the public, the ‘frontline workers’, are highly autonomous and make arrangements on the field on a case-by-case basis (DUBOIS 2012; LIPSKY 1981) . Do we think that teachers, educators, doctors and LI staff, when they are questioned in an evaluation, don't have an agenda and messages they want to get across (PERRET 2008)? Do we think that they do not have an opinion on the public policies in which they are involved? If an evaluation is to be truly relevant, then we need to do more than just question them; we need to work with them to define the questions to be asked, share analytical frameworks such as programme theories¹⁵, and collectively interpret the results.

4.2 Integrating conflict

In considering that the PE should be a place for deliberation, we suggest that evaluation should remain a place for reasonable discussion, in which everyone can express themselves and put forward their arguments, putting their prejudices at a distance. Conflict is certainly possible, but it is confined to given subjects and it must be possible, *in the end*, to reach common conclusions. In the evaluation (1), when we set up the citizens' panel, the recruiter was instructed to avoid people who were politically involved, for example. We often advised local authorities launching their first PE to choose participants *intuitu personae*, persons who would play the game of participation. In this sense, we are in line with the vision of the deliberative model, theorised in the works of Jürgen Habermas or John Rawls, a model of governance that asserts the primacy of the “principle of discussion” in solving social problems. In this model, it is the public arena and civil society that identify social problems, and then judge the collective interest of addressing them and constructing

15 Programme theories include all the assumptions that are being made about the expected consequences of an evaluated intervention, and when, how and why they might work.

a response. This model is underpinned by the idea that we share a common liberal culture, which means that we fear conflict and are prepared to compromise to avoid it¹⁶.

How far are we going wrong? **We live in an age where conflict is at the heart of political debate, but we do not know how to involve the actors who defend their positions through conflict.** How can we involve animal rights activists in an evaluation of the law on the slaughter of animals? Feminists, Green activists who favour direct action, but also religious traditionalists or nationalists?

We need to be able to ask ourselves this question. Without claiming to have ready-made solutions, we suggest below a few ways of incorporating conflict into our evaluations.

Firstly, **we need to be able to identify conflicts.** The idea of mapping controversies¹⁷ is useful in this respect. Upstream of the PE process, a controversy mapping would make it possible to understand what the conflicts are about and how they affect the 'public affair' to be discussed. By identifying the actors involved, it could lead to a fairly radical change in the points of view having a say, and facilitate exchanges based on a better mutual understanding. But an evaluation based on controversy mapping would not just broaden and facilitate participation; it could fundamentally alter the scope of the evaluation to focus on what really matters (i.e. what is controversial). For example, an evaluation would no longer focus on scattered measures aimed at improving water quality, but on everyone's right to drink quality water (and on the way in which public action, in general, affects this right). This is a major point: in our experience, it is hard to involve stakeholders who are in conflict with the public authorities, partly because they refuse to fit into the limited scope of the evaluation and rather want to position themselves at the level of society as a whole.

This investigative work can also be carried out by the members of the committee themselves, as a way of broadening their horizons, exposing themselves to a much more intimate understanding of the public problems and related evaluation challenges, becoming aware of their own position in the debates, and investing this awareness in the evaluative work. There are already integrated approaches in the social sciences based on conflict analysis (BIERSCHENK AND OLIVIER DE SARDAN 1994), but these are perhaps yet to be invented for public action and its evaluation. In both cases, this argues for an open approach in which the scope of the analysis is initially broad, and the objects of evaluative investigation gradually specified.

A second approach is to discuss the rules of the debate itself. It is far from certain that the most polarised actors would agree to take part in a PE. These groups may prefer to keep to themselves, to preserve their identity and be able to express their

16 For a discussion of the theories of Rawls and Habermas and the consequences for political deliberation, see Bernard Manin (1985, 19-20). On the implications of the deliberative model for our view of conflict in society, see Loïc Blondiaux (2008).

17 This term, proposed by Bruno Latour, describes a pedagogical exercise aimed at investigating contemporary socio-technical debates. In particular, it implies a cartographic representation of these controversies (VENTURINI 2008). We use it here in the sense of an investigation into the actors involved in controversies, with the aim of establishing the different versions of what is happening and what is at stake in public action.

concerns freely. They may also see participation as a trap, a way of legitimising a policy of which they disapprove. It is therefore necessary to consider that the first subject of the participation process is the form it will take, the outputs it will produce and the way in which they will be used, so as to build the trust necessary to hold a PE. In this way, parallel processes can be envisaged, whether continuous or at specific moments, enabling everyone to contribute actively to the evaluation without always being involved.

A third possibility relates to what we can expect from the PE. Should the aim be to arrive at a consensual judgement or a final reconciliation? It is possible that a PE could document the disagreements and show what is acceptable to all the stakeholders and what remains in the realm of conflict and why.

A final option would be to support 'militant evaluations', i.e. evaluations carried out by militant groups in the light of their own values (TEVINI forthcoming). An effort could then be made to reconcile these evaluations with those carried out by the authorities, in the form of consensus conferences, along the lines of what has been done in France in the field of education (MONS 2018) .

4.3 Making participatory evaluations the starting point for profound changes in public action

If we are talking about the inclusion of all actors, including those who are not 'stakeholders' and who are subjected to public policies, or who are in open conflict with them, it is because PE has great potential to be a driving force in the democratic developments of our societies, to represent a 'counterforce' to the rise of populism and to oppose it with deliberation (PICCIOTTO 2018) . This potential exists, and tomorrow's PEs may lead to more profound reconfigurations of public action, where participation calls for participation.

We need to take responsibility, and use the room for manoeuvre we have to promote participation. But we also need to find allies - elected representatives, public agents, stakeholders, citizens - who are prepared to try, experiment and test: the methods exist, but it's their implementation in real contexts that's important, and that's where we really need to develop expertise to develop modest but useful EPs. To quote Claire Hutchings: "[We need to turn] Ferraris into well-functioning Fiats" (2016). Here's a programme to ensure that participation is no longer an innovation, but becomes the new normal.

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